

Assessment of Learning Environment of Early Childhood Education Centers in Nassarawa Local Government Area, Kano State

*Tukur, Abdullahi Ph.D.¹

Tel: +2348069581011

El-Yakub, Maryam²

Tel: +2348169124659

¹Department of Academic Support Services, Federal University of Agriculture Zuru, Kebbi State

²Department of Education Early Childhood Care Education, Sa'adatu Rimi University of Education Kumbotso, Kano State

Abstract

The study examined early childhood learning environment in Early Childhood Education Centers (ECCE) in Nassarawa Local Government Area (LGA), Kano State. The researcher used survey research method to collect data from the target population. A total of three schools were used for the study. The objectives of the study were; to ascertain the safety of the learning environment of child care centres, to determine the available age-appropriate equipment and facilities in early childhood centers, and to establish the caregiver-pupil ratio in the centres. To accomplish the objectives of this study, data was collected through the researcher-formulated scale called Questionnaire for Assessing Learning Environment (QALE) whose reliability coefficient was estimated at 0.72. Findings obtained from the analysis of the data collected revealed that the equipment and facilities in all centers sampled had issues with safety checks. The equipment and facilities were however, age appropriate, but the care-giver: child ratio was found wanting and does not conform with the NCE minimum standard. Based on the findings, it is recommended that stakeholders should try to maintain the equipment and facilities to reduce the safety risks and threats posed by them. They should also bridge the gap of care-giver: child ratio by training more care-givers. The study recommends further research is needed to expose the early childhood learning environment and their needs, so as to have the basic and necessary requirements to operate.

Keywords: Learning Environment, ECCE, Age-appropriate Equipment, Caregiver-Pupil Ratio

Introduction

Children need to grow and reach their full potential, in order to realize this, there is the need for them to be properly cared for in the right way through Early Childhood Care and Education Programmes. Child Development is holistic in nature; thus, it covers all aspect of human life. Early childhood is the most vital stage in human development, it is a stage that begins from conception to eight years age and thus it is the stage for almost all the development of children and especially brain development.

Adequate care in the early years are crucial to the proper development of children,

Early Childhood Education (ECE) is seen as the education of children before they start primary school as stated in the National Policy on Education (Federal Republic of Nigeria 2013:11). Oduolowu cited in Oduolowu (2001) sees Early Childhood Education as a “branch of knowledge and an essential component of all family and program arrangements for young children from birth to statutory age of six”. Early childhood education provides opportunity for

children to develop fully, by exposing them to the right elements that are crucial to their development which will determine lifelong outcomes. According to Haggie and Shwamut cited in Korb (2018) early childhood education is “designed to enhance learning and development of young children”. It is a period which cares for the holistic development of children. Brain cells growth and the structuring of neural connections in the brain all occur at the first years of life. The kind of care and nurture that the child received which includes the nutritional, health and safety, social and emotional, cognitive and communicative will determine how he develops to reach his potential.

The rights of the child to proper development and equal opportunity should be given to all children irrespective of their race, gender and parental economic status as expressed in so many conventions and declarations. The CRC (1989) particularly states in Article 2 that states shall ensure the right of every child is respected and protected.

Education International (EI) (1998) (World Congress in Washington D.C.), pledged to promote and pressure governments to provide quality Early Childhood Education (ECE) to every child, free and to enrich the conditions of educators. With this in mind the study aims to investigate the opportunities that are present in different sets of centres being studied. Which will bring to light the kind of differences that exists and hopefully will help the stake-holders take proper action, and towards making the centre that lacks adequate infrastructure and qualified staff better so that all children will have equal chance of making something of themselves and thereby be useful to the society at large.

The learning centres in Kano state with particular reference to Nassarawa local

government are operated by both state primary schools and private primary schools. The centres covered by the study are state funded. Most of the centres covered for this study presented a picture that needs to be addressed. The centres are not up to standard, they lack the basic requirements to operate, as proposed in the minimum standard on early childhood education. Inadequate infrastructure like tables and chairs that are not age appropriate, unsafe learning environment that does not conform to the standard set by the national curriculum. The care-giver student ratio is very high a class has about 45-50 pupils with 1 or 2 care-givers.

Childhood is a period of learning, experiences, and fun. As recognized in the CRC (1989) it is the legal obligation of the government and rights of the child to ensure survival, protection, health and education irrespective of their gender, social status, religion and others. The declaration of Sustainable Development Goals (UN SDG) 2015 agenda 4.2 states that by 2030 all girls and boys have access to quality early childhood development care. Some children are being excluded from these experiences because their centres do not have conducive learning environment equipped with proper equipment and facilities in their centres. This is contrary to the doctrines of all child conventions which clearly states the need for making all children equal with equal opportunity to thrive and grow to their full potential.

Early childhood is the period of growth, development and learning. Children need a stimulating environment that will help them develop and learn successfully. The childhood environment therefore, consist of all the activities and conditions, circumstances and influences surrounding and affecting the learning of a child. It includes the physical environment, socio-

emotional environment, and cultural environment.

Childhood care education centre should be made in such a way that it will contribute to the development and learning of children in all domains. Children learn from birth and develop in such a way that whatever they come across in the environment may have a significant influence on their optimal development. It is in this respect that the Early Years Foundation Stage (EYFS 2009) asserted that provision of high-quality learning environment helps children to develop confident personalities which lay the foundations for becoming successful learners.

Children begin learning from conception and it continues throughout life. Gopnik cited in Korb (2018) asserts that “childhood is for learning” and that children are designed to learn. Several studies show that children use their minds in a special way to learn even better than adults. Children use all the available resources in the environment to learn, explore and utilise to make their development successful. DeBoard et al. cited in Goodling (2016) asserts that “children learn by interacting with other children, adults, objects, and natural materials found in the environment”

Early childhood care learning environment is an enabling environment which can support the child’s optimal development, it includes a healthy and safe environment, supportive and affectionate interaction, appropriate modelling, stimulation., protection, and time which are all components of the child’s right. This assessment asserts that “children learn by interacting with other children, adults, objects, and natural materials found in the environment” (DeBoard et al. cited in Goodling 2016). Early childhood centres need to be made conducive to effectively deliver the objectives of the centres. The

learning environment in childhood centres has a significant influence on the learning of children as cited by Jones and Lesaux cited in Schradin (2018) “a child’s learning environment can have a deep, lasting impact on her core non-academic skills.” A conducive Learning environment should send the message of love to the children, of having secure relationships with caring and responsive adults, where they feel safe and free to explore and learn.

The learning environment consist of the physical environment, relationship between the caregiver and pupils. Care-givers have an important role in providing the conducive environment for learning. They must ensure that children feel loved and valued as individuals, safe and cared for. Their rate of development should be respected, they are not rushed but reinforced in measures that are appropriate for each child. Children’s time must be managed so that they have the opportunity to become deeply involved in their activities and to follow their ideas through, including returning later to continue their explorations or creative expressions. Care-givers must regulate activities, plan different and stimulating experiences to promote learning along with opportunities for children to revisit, practise or enjoy the experiences.

Having the above in place, it is then the care-givers skilful interactions with the children which will move learning forward. When children are learning in nature, they become more confident and have higher self-esteem because they can manage the environment in which they live, play, and explore. Their sense of self-worth increases and they become more aware of their surroundings (Nilsen cited in Yalçın 2015).

The Indoor Environment is hereby referred to as the classroom. The arrangement of the classroom environment should be made by considering the size of the room, the

diversity of the children, daily routines, care-giver: child ratio and learning areas. The classroom environment is the most basic and necessary element for all children to learn effectively. It has been advocated the environment be arranged to provide sufficient opportunities for learning and enough space should be given between chairs and equipment to make movement between the different areas in the classroom easy, Greenberg & Rodriguez cited in Worthington (2008). According to Partnership, cited in Hensley-Pipkin (2015) “Designing a classroom environment which provides students with enjoyable, deep, thoughtful, relevant, and engaging learning experiences which broaden their worldviews will likely aid students in gaining the skills associated with the Common Core State Standards.”

The National Association for the Education of Young Children (NAEYC) believes it is the duty of educators to support and promote the development and learning of all Children through the setting up of a classroom that is appropriate and conducive for learning. (Bredenkamp & Copple, cited in Hensley 2010). Classrooms shall be solid structures that will not collapse. NCE minimum standard gave the following as conditions for making the classroom.

The buildings shall be child-friendly and should not pose dangers to the child physically and health-wise. - Size: Enough Space; the floor to be at least 16 square metres for 10–15 children. - Design: Bearing in mind the human kinetic behaviour of children, enough space should be provided to allow for free movement. - Ventilation: The classroom should be well ventilated. - Illumination: The classroom should have wide

and adequate number of windows (3 on each side of the wall) to enable children see well and clearly every part of the room..... the seating arrangements can be, circular, semi-circular, isolated groupings, triangular, rectangular, etc. - Corners: For science, health and nutrition. Sleeping Room: To isolate and protect children that need sleep.

Ancheita (2005) asserts that classrooms can be apportioned into different zones such as the quiet zone, messy zone, and active zone. “The quiet zone typically includes spaces such as reading, listening, manipulatives, writing, small blocks and math. The messy zone has water, sand, clay, painting, collage, science and a nature area. The active zone has large blocks, dramatic play, music and gross-motor skill activities (Olds, cited in Ancheita 2005)”. Oduolowu (2011) asserts that the typical learning areas indoors are creative area, language area, maths and sciences, dramatic play area, music and movement play, library area, block area, sand and water area, and computer area.

The outdoor environment also referred to as the playground is the environment that surrounds the centre, it consists of all the elements present outside the classroom. It is an important extension of indoor classroom learning; it is valuable ‘in promoting the development of gross motor skills. Ihn cited in Buckley (2011) asserts that “play in outdoor environments is not only imperative for the physical well-being, but also important for enhancing social interactions, as well as a child’s cognitive, social, and emotional skills”. The playground environment stimulates, excites the children and make them feel free to explore and experiment with a lot of things.

Playgarden cited in Asaji (2018) opines that Playground facilities challenge and stimulate children giving them new experiences each time they play.

The equipment mostly found outdoors includes the slides, see-saw, trampoline, swings, tunnels, and sand baskets. According to Karim & Paul cited in Asaji (2018) playground facilities include climbing structures, swings, slides and spring riders. The minimum standard for Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) states the following, as the equipment to be provided in the playground.

Swings - Rocking boats -
Merry-go-rounds - Slides -
Sand-pit/box - Water-play
bowls - See-saw - Climbing
frame - Space for story telling
- Garden for nature work -
Tricycle - Beans bags -
Rocking horses - Skipping
ropes - Balls, etc

Early childhood learning environment offers children the variety of chances for the development of both gross and fine motor skills. Gross motor skills include the development of large muscles which are needed for walking, jumping, climbing and running. The fine motor skills include the development of small muscles needed for holding, moulding, writing, and painting. The fine motor skills are established in the use of loose parts like play dough, and sandbox.

Language skills are developed as children interact with care-givers and peers in all the activities carried out in the centres. Social skills are improved when children engage in communication and interactions between themselves and their care-givers, through expressions on like saying please, sorry, and thank you. A research conducted by Miller, Tichota, & White, (2013) identified the social and intrapersonal, kinesthetic, visual-spatial, and math skills the

children were developed when exposed to quality learning environment. Wilson (2012) recognised the importance the outdoor learning environment as significant in promoting children and their connections with and about nature. Children cognitive development is highly improved by the quality and variety of the equipment, materilas and loose parts that are available to explore and manipulate in the learning environment. Loose parts are materials that can be synthetic or natural, but are open ended and can be moved and arranged as children choose.

Families expect childcare centres to be safe, According to Wellhousen 2002 cited in 53567 -ch 10 pdf. Parents assume that the playground equipment, toys and other materials will be safe and the teachers will carefully supervise their activities. When the environment is safe children, performances is measured by 25% (Chu cited in Braden 2017). A safe learning environment is one in which precaution is taken to ensure no child comes to harm, all facilities, equipment and learning areas are in good working condition, it should be designed to support the Childs' holistic development. As stated in the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC), the Salamanca Statement, Declaration of the World on Education for All (EFA), children, by reason of their physical and mental vulnerability, need special safeguards and care. With this in mind care centres should work towards ensuring their centres are protected from all foreseen and unforeseen hazards that might in any way affect the children while in the childhood care learning environment. It is expected that the caregiver will be conscious of the safety of the children when arranging the classroom. National Association for Education of Young Children (NAEYC, 1998) focus largely on safety issues in respect to the outdoor environment, precisely in

regards to supervision, impact, fall zones and hazards. According to Braden (2017) childcare centres should use toys that are very durable, nontoxic and -too large to swallow, free of small or removable parts, free of sharp material and edges, free of toxic materials, nonelectric, flame resistant to ensure safety of children in the learning centres.

Outdoor play facilities are usually exposed to adverse weather. Direct sunlight heats up bare metal slides and may cause serious contact burn injuries. To reduce the impact of the sun, bare metal slides should have an anchored shelter. Alternatively, insulation materials such as plastic or wood may be used (Public Playground Safety Handbook, 2015). To ensure safety the NCE minimum standard states that doors should open outward for safety, and netted against harmful insects such as mosquitoes, and Flooring of the classroom should be smooth but not slippery. Objects and toys children play with should be too large to swallow, - free of sharp material and edges, -suitable for the child's abilities, non-electric, -free of brittle materials that could break during play. Play-ground equipment should be free from rust, sharp edges and weather friendly.

The equipment, which include chairs, tables, utensil, stationary and all other materials needed in the environment should be made specially to suit the child's age, height and weight. If the equipment are not age appropriate it may cause some hazards and serious injuries to the children. Montessori cited in Hensley-Pipkin 2015 asserts that casa bambini should have "child-sized furniture, open-shelves, and high-quality materials are fundamental elements of the early childhood classroom". Overall, the environment needs to be developmentally appropriate for the children to be effective to in achieving the objective of the centres. Braden (2017) asserts that age appropriate equipment should be designed, ensuring that

the equipment being used is appropriate for the children that are using it, as well as encouraging learning that will help build fundamental skills. The layout of the area should also meet the proper criteria for developmental needs of the children. Equipment maintenance can be easily avoided, yet is the primary cause of injuries. Keeping a good maintained play area prevents injuries as well as keeps the equipment lasting longer.

The classroom should be arranged in a way that creates minimal accident possibilities. Chu, cited in Braden (2017) "Children are likely to face seven major safety and threat issues within classroom: mechanical, physiological, chemical, emotional, thermal, organic, and electric threats" Inappropriate age equipment according to Chu results in physiological threats may cause physical injuries such as muscle strains due to using excessive force or maladjusted sitting positions. Mechanical injuries are those that occur as a result of colliding with edges of tables or throwing of hard or rough objects or surfaces. Chemical from chemical substances and cause irritation and allergic reaction, emotional occurs as a result of stressful environments, thermal result from heat, such as a fire, or hot objects. Organic injuries are from harmful organisms, such as, the flu, or a virus, and electric threats which are from electrical materials.

Social interactions of children help them learn and develop to their full potential with this notion in mind it is stated in the National Policy on Education (FGN, 2014) that the teacher: pupil ratio of 1:25 with a helper/an assistant for the pre-primary class. As this is likely to be of great support to the development of the child. Too high a ratio is likely to present a problem in the sense that the developmental characteristics and the needs of the pre-schoolers is abundant. Children at this stage are impatient,

extremely spirited and energy to expend. They are still reliant on adults for almost all their basic needs – physical, intellectual, language, emotional and social skills – and therefore they require their full attention and diverse activities to help to satisfy their basic needs. It therefore becomes imperative that care-giver: child ratio be such that they will have ample time to communicate and thus have a chance to influence their development and learning. As Vygotsky's (1978) social constructivist theory postulate that children learn through interacting with the environment and through social interaction with others. This theory focuses on the role of social interactions in the learning process and this is not possible if there are too many children the care-giver will have to care for. This brings us to making sure the care-giver: child ratio is such that it is manageable for optimal performance.

Many psychologists and authorities who study human behaviour have proposed that learning occurs as a result of human interaction between himself and his environment. Proponents of this thought includes Liv Vygotsky's (1978) whose social constructivist theory advocates that children learn through interacting with the environment and through social interaction with others. Vygotsky's social development theory, which focuses on the role of social interactions in the learning process, is a founding principle of constructivism. Vygotsky's theory suggests cognitive development is highly promoted during interactions between the child, environment, objects found in the environment and other members of the society, who help shape and promote the learning process for the children.

According to Vygotsky, children learn to create meaning to what happen around them through the construct of their environment by learning from more experienced and knowledgeable member of

the society, this makes social learning in the classroom a mutual process of learning between the children- teachers on the one hand and children -peers on the other. Thus, Vygotsky proposes the zone of proximal development, the point at which the child can independently do something and the point at which he can do something with some assistance from a more experienced person.

Vygotsky's learning theory supports the value of creating a democratic learning community within the classroom through the establishment of a sense of safety and security, collaborative experiences, the sharing of ideas, and group project work. Social interaction and learning can be encouraged and supported by the physical classroom design (Carter cited in Hensley-Pipkin 2015).

The Regio Emilia philosophy was founded by Loris Malaguzzi and named it after Reggio Emilia an area in northern Italy. This philosophy focused on the learning environment of the child. According to this approach environments affect our growth, development and learning. The Reggio Emilia approach to early childhood education recognizes the enormous influence of the environment on our learning by referring to it as the "third teacher". This approach asserts that children are energetic learners and their interests should direct care givers when planning their learning environment, they should look at how the environment is organised and resources provided. Regio Emilia approach believes that the environment effect on the learning of the child is very vital therefore teachers are urged to make sure the environment is arranged to support the inquisitive nature of the child, to make him want to explore, experiment and learn. The approach divided the environment into different learning areas, this includes the art, drama, 3D models light, shadows (Brodie 2013).

According to this view, “the classroom environment is not only a space for learning, but a space for living in which students, teachers, families, and community members collaborate in the learning process (Hensley-Pipkin 2015)”. Maria Montessori was among the first pioneers of kindergarten. She developed “Casa Bambini” “children’s garden”. Montessori was amazed by how children got interested in the environment which makes them learn through exploring it. According to Montessori the teachers are there to support and encourage the children learn, they should arrange the environment in such a way as to make everything easily accessible to the children. The children will be free to explore and learn by themselves. The classroom is designed to allow movement and collaboration, as it also promotes concentration and a sense of order.

Exclusive learning materials are displayed on the shelves which are made to fit the age of the children, easily accessed by the children. Thus, making them interested in exploring and taking interest in what they see around them. Hensley-Pipkin (2015) child-sized furniture, open-shelves, and high-quality materials are fundamental elements of the early childhood classroom. “Educators should also recognize the importance of modelling appropriate use of materials, allowing students to make personal choices, and providing adequate time and space for exploration and use of materials (Wolf cited in Hensley-Pipkin 2015)”

American Montessori Society (AMS 2018) asserts that Montessori approach offers children opportunities to develop their potential, the become engaged, competent, responsible, and respectful citizens with an understanding and appreciation that learning is for life. The teachers in Montessori ‘casa bambini’ therefore, provide environments where students have the freedom and the

tools to pursue answers to their own questions (AMS 2018).

Montessori learning areas are divided into four (Oduolowu 2011) the practical life area, sensory area, academic area and the cultural or artistic area. The practical life area of the learning environment is made to care of self, work habits, development of social behaviours and movement. The sensory area fosters the development of the five senses through interaction with different kinds of sensorial materials, soft, hard, rough and many more. The academic area is made up of materials that help develop language and mathematics skills of the children with things like moveable alphabets, tools for tracing, objects to show shape, size and quantity. The cultural and artistic area help children explore their culture, art and nature, through music, history and art.

Urie Bronfenbrenner (1972) proposed ecological systems theory which emphasizes the vital role environment plays in child development and learning. The interactions between a child and his environment according to Bronfenbrenner (1972) consists of systems which are interconnected. The relationship is bi-directional which produces a reaction and thus, learning occurs. Therefore, a rich environment is vital for effective learning. Bronfenbrenner cited in Berk (2008) sees the environment as composed of a series of nested structures which are interrelated and connected, it consists of the immediate family, school, and neighbourhood which children spend their lives. Each layer of the system directly or indirectly affects child’s development. The Mesosystem is the layer that consist of the immediate family, the childcare centre and neighbourhood play area. The other systems are Microsystem which is the innermost level consisting of activities that are present in the immediate environment of the child. The Exosystem is

third level and consist of the activities that are indirectly affected by the child. The Macro system is the last system and consists of the cultural values and beliefs laws, custom, and resources. Berk (2008).

The early learning environment as seen from several researches is very vital in ensuring the holistic development of the child, it promotes social, moral, cognitive and physical development. The environment consists of different learning areas and they all help support the child. Areas like the mathematics, sensory, the arts and crafts, literacy, blocks and others. The centres that do not have or have inadequate and inappropriate equipment, will be of little use to the children as the ultimate goal of the learning environment is to help support and promote children development and learning. If the environment fails to meet up with the prerequisite needed to operate the government and other stakeholders will need to come to the aid of the centres in form of intervention. So as to have effective centres that will be of useful to the children and society at large.

Children grow and develop where they receive care in a learning environment which offers the most quality child care with the provision of appropriate equipment and tools. As most of the psychologist who studied children observed that the environment has a vital role to play in the development of children in the early years which will invariably affect them when they grow.

The Early childhood centres in Nasarawa local government are mostly faced with the problem of having an environment that is not conducive. A conducive environment is supposed to help the children develop to their full potential. It is to be a high-quality environment, well planned, with stimulating objects that will support children learning, where they can feel safe, free to

explore and learn, have relationships with caring and responsive adults. Observation has shown that many early childcare centers in Kano State are poorly equipped with learning materials. And that those with a relatively conducive environment, their equipment are largely not age-appropriate and learning facilities are grossly inadequate to meet the NCCE Minimum Standard requirement of caregiver-pupil ratio. While this problem persists in Kano State, research report on the assessment of learning environment of ECCE in Nasarawa LGA is rare. This study therefore attempts at bridging the gap.

Objectives of the study

The specific objectives of this study are:

1. To ascertain the safety of the learning environment of child care centres.
2. To determine the available age-appropriate equipment and facilities in early childhood centres.
3. To establish the caregiver: pupil ratio in the centres.

Research Questions

1. To what extent is the learning environment of children in ECCE centers in Nassarawa LGA?
2. Are there adequate age-appropriate learning and caregiving facilities in the ECCE Centres in Nassarawa LGA?
3. What is the extent of caregiver: pupil ratio in ECCE centres in Nassarawa LGA?

Methodology

Laverty (2016) asserts that survey research collects data in a pre-determined format from all or part of a population to assess the relative incidence, distribution, and interrelations of naturally occurring variables. Questions can be open-ended or closed resulting in a combination of both qualitative and quantitative data. The method

provides participants with a high level of confidentiality and anonymity which can solicit more honest responses; however, the high level of anonymity makes it difficult to ensure a representative sample. Bhattacharjee (2012) views survey research as a method that uses consistent questionnaires or interviews to collect data about people and their preferences, thoughts, and behaviours in a systematic manner.

The population of the study consist of all schools that offer early childhood classes in Kano state but with particular reference to those in Nasarawa local government. The child learning centers in kano, according to UNICEF Annual Census (2019) are 5283 centers with boys enrolment at 28600 and girls 33000. All the centers in Kano are found in the primary schools that operate in the state. A class is just set aside or in some schools two classes are set aside depending on the number of pupils that registered for the ECCE class. Nasarawa Local Government has 225 number of centers (UNICEF census 2019). Out of which only 3 three centers will be used as this study sample. The three centers used for the study were selected

Sampling means taking any segment of a population as a representative of the whole. A sample is part of a population that is studied to reach conclusions about the entire population. Dada (2016 pg,235) opines that “the sample has to be representative of the larger group to obtain a composite profile of that population”. For the purpose of this study the sample consist of three centers that are located at Nasarawa local government. The SRPS, RCPS and MTPS. The sampling technique used for the study was the purposive sampling technique. Purposive sampling technique is one in which the researcher uses own judgement in selection of members (Dada 2016). The respondents of the questionnaire are the head teachers of the selected centers.

The instrument used in data collection for this study was the questionnaire which was constructed by the researcher specifically for the study. It is titled Questionnaire for Assessing Learning Environment (QALE). To ensure the questionnaire is reliable and valid it was first used in a pilot study which was conducted by the researcher on some randomly selected schools. The questions that were not clear were explained by the researcher herself to the participants of the pilot study, thus all elements of ambiguity were cleared. The questionnaire was then revised and all corrections were made before it was administered to the sample population of the study. To ensure validity the instrument used was prepared and handed over to the project supervisor to critically analyse, make observations, corrections and suggestions. This process made the study achieve content validity. Cohen et al. cited in Brodie (2013) defines validity as the honesty, depth, richness, and scope of the data collected in the area under investigation.

The instrument shows reliability from the pilot study conducted by the researcher. For the pilot study two schools were used and they asked for clarification on questions they did not understand, after wards the researcher re-examined the questionnaire and made necessary corrections to make it clearer and better understood by the respondents. The reliability index obtained from the pilot study was measured using Cronbach’s Alpha. The instrument was found to be positively correlated at $r=0.76$. which is considered adequate for a newly developed scale, this proved the questionnaire was reliable.

The researcher first went to the schools to request for permission to use their early learning classes in conducting the research from the school authority. After which the researcher then went to the school the following week to conduct the research

by administering the questionnaire. The questionnaire was administered by the researcher to the different centers, and the participants responded by answering the questions. The questionnaire was divided into two parts, the demographic information of the care-givers and the part which asks questions on the early learning center. The questionnaire has close ended questions with options to be chosen, some have yes and no options, some others have to be ticked or circled, while others have multiple responses, which the respondent can choose as many as it pertains to that particular learning center

like the types of equipment and or infrastructure they have at the center.

Data analysis summarizes the data so as to provide the answers to the questions and make the reader understand what was presented in the study. Dada (2016) asserts that “in order to do this, researchers must carefully examine their data, they must become friends with their data”. The method of Data analysis for this study was the mean score, graphs and percentages. Tabular presentation was adopted which makes a large data be presented and read easily.

Results

Research question 1

To what extent is the learning environment of children in ECCE centers in Nassarawa LGA?

Table 1: Extent of safety of learning equipment in ECCE centers in Nassarawa LGA

Safety of equipment	Frequency/Center	Percentage
Rust on metal or sharp materials	1	20
Broken equipment or small objects	2	40
Slippery or rough floor	2	40
Total	5	100

Source: research data collected 2021

The study found that most of the centers visited had some safety issue, the first center SRPS has rough and an uneven floor that can make children fall and injure themselves, the next Center was found to have many broken and rusty equipment, have sharp material and edges which can make the children injure self or others, the last center showed faulty slides that can be hazardous to the children. Keeping the centers safe is the number one priority.

To ensure safety the NCE minimum standard states that doors should open outward for safety, and netted against harmful insects such as mosquitoes, and Flooring of the classroom should be smooth but not slippery. Objects should be too large to swallow, centres should be free of sharp material and edges, free of brittle materials that could break during play. This showed that the research question to ascertain the safety of the centres was proven to be confirmed at the centres.

Research question 2

Are there adequate age-appropriate learning and caregiving facilities in the ECCE Centres in Nassarawa LGA?

Table 1: Adequacy of age-appropriate equipment in ECCE centers in Nassarawa LGA

Safety of equipment	No available	No of age-appropriateness	Percentage
Chairs and Tables	75	74	98.7
Shelves	70	69	98.6
Play materials/environment	53	50	94.3

Text Books	112	112	100
Audio-visual aids	35	29	82.8

Source: research data collected 2021

All the centers visited had age-appropriate equipment both indoors and outdoors, like chairs, tables play equipment. They all complied with the age of the children. As indicated in Table 2 above, 98.7

percent of the chairs and tables available in the centers are age-appropriate. This is the same with shelves (98.6%), play materials (94.3%), books (100%) and audio-visual aids (82.8%).

Research question 3

What is the extent of caregiver: pupil ratio in ECCE centres in Nassarawa LGA?

Table 3: Care-giver: child ratio

Caregiver-child ratio	Number of children in the class.	Frequency	Percentage
1:10	05-10	-	-
1:20	10-20	1	20
1:30	21-30	-	-
1:40	31-40	4	80
Total		5	100

Source: research data collected 2021

The above table shows that 80% of the centers have high number of children in the classes while only 20 % have few numbers of children in the class. The high number of children in the centers show that the amount of attention and care given to the children will not be sufficient due to the fact that the number of children is high in a class, being highly energetic and restless there is need for an adequate number to make sure they are well cared for.

The caregiver child ratio was found to be a bit high in all the centers studied, the Minimum standard specifically said the ratio should be 1:25 with a helper/an assistant. It was found that in all the centers there was only one caregiver per class without an assistant or helper. This is bound to make the caregiver not be able to carry out their duties to the best of their capability because of the number of children they need to look after.

Discussion of findings

Early childhood learning environment is an environment meant for the holistic development of children, therefore

creating an area that allows young children to flourish in education is an in-depth process. The study was aimed at examining the safety, age-appropriate equipment and the caregiver: child ratio in the learning centres. The safety issue found in the study shows that all the three-target population are hazardous to the children as they were found to contain sharp, broken, rusty equipment and rough flooring of some classrooms. This as the NCE minimum standard states that doors should open outward for safety, and netted against harmful insects such as mosquitoes, and Flooring of the classroom should be smooth but not slippery. Care-givers should conduct periodic checking for loose nuts and bolts and broken, rusty, or sharp parts should be done (A.A. P. 2016).

The study found that all the centers have age-appropriate equipment and facilities in accordance with Montessori, who asserts that casa bambini should have “child-sized furniture, open-shelves, and high-quality materials are fundamental elements of the early childhood classroom”. Overall, the environment needs to be developmentally

appropriate for the children to be effective to in achieving the objective of the centres.

The third question answered was on the Care-giver: child ratio in the early childhood learning environment. Care-giver: child ratio is however not in conformity with the NMS which states that care-giver: child ratio in Nigeria should be 1: 25, but for most of the centres study was conducted they had 1:40 ratio.

Conclusion

The findings in the study shows that most of the centers lack what is needed to run a learning center, both indoor and outdoor environments do not have adequate, qualitative and safe facilities and equipment. The care-giver: child ratio also needs addressed. The equipment and facilities are age appropriate but need to be maintained. The stakeholders should take into consideration the importance of early childhood learning centers in helping and supporting child growth and survival, which is holistic in nature, thus it cuts across all aspects of life, cognitive development, socio-emotional development, language development and physical development.

Recommendations

1. The government should provide adequate funding to the childhood centres to ensure availability and maintenance of the childhood centers, safety and health of the children is key to achieving optimal development, care-giver development so as to fill the gap of care-giver: child ratio that is such a big issue in all the centres studied, with periodic supervision of the activities of the childhood centers by government officials.
2. The Non-governmental organizations should come into the activities of the childhood care centers that need help, by supporting them with care- givers

development, learning materials like books, charts, slides etc., play materials both indoor and outdoor like swings, balls, slides, see-saw, and merry -go - round.

3. The community at large should put hands together and improve the condition of centers by helping with periodic visits to the centers to see what form of help can be rendered. They can help mend broken equipment, clean the surrounding, and to help them improvisation and making equipment using easily available materials found in the environment, like swings with bamboo sticks and used tires.

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